

A STUDY ON CLASSROOM TEACHER CANDIDATES' CONCERN FOR NON-APPOINTMENT AND THEIR TEACHING MOTIVATIONⁱ

Hülya Hamurcu,
Tuncay Canbulatⁱⁱ,
Necip Beyhan,
Elif İlhan

Dokuz Eylül University,
Buca Faculty of Education,
Department of Elementary Education,
İzmir, Turkey

Abstract:

One of the important elements of the education system is teacher and success of the education system is mainly based on the fact that teachers who will run the system have expected competencies. While the process of bringing teachers in competencies expected from them is seen important in the 21st century world, it is also important to run the appointment process of teachers in a healthy way. It is thought that current teacher appointment system of Turkey causes teachers to get concerned and this affects their motivation for teaching adversely. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the concern of teachers for non-appointment and their motivation for teaching. This study was designed in the screening model. Target population of the study is fourth-grade teacher candidates studying Classroom Teaching Department of five different Faculties of Education in Aegean, Black Sea and Marmara Region of Turkey in 2017-2018 academic year. The sample of the study consists of 370 teacher candidates selected by simple random sampling method. In the study, the "Non-Appointment Concern of Classroom Teacher Candidates"ⁱⁱⁱ was measured by "Teacher Candidates Non-Appointment Concern scale" developed by Eskici (2016) and the teaching motivation was measured by "Teaching Motivation Scale" adapted to Turkish by Candan and Evin Gencil (2015). Analysis of the research data was done by SPSS v.22 packaged software, and ANOVA and t-test techniques were used. According to the results of the study, non-appointment concern of classroom teacher candidates has been found to be at a moderate level and significant differences have been determined by universities. Although the concern is above moderate level, it has been determined that teacher candidates do not lose their teaching motivation and their teaching motivation points

ⁱ This article is presented as an oral presentation at the 2nd International Symposium of Limitless Education and Research (ISLER 2018).

ⁱⁱ Correspondence: email tuncaycanbulat@gmail.com

are still above moderate level. In addition, it has been determined that the motivation of teacher candidates varies significantly by universities. There has been no significant difference between genders in both variables. It is believed that this study will contribute to improvement of the 21st century teachers' competencies and will create an environment of data driven thinking and discussion based on the related variables.

Keywords: Turkey, classroom teacher candidate, concern for non-appointment, teaching motivation

1. Introduction

Pre-service training process of teachers, which is one of the elements of the education system, and appointment issues have been studied for years. The fact that many teacher candidates graduated from the Department of Classroom Teaching in recent years, and the graduated candidates who are waiting for appointment led to "*non-appointment concern*" in candidates (Baştürk, 2007, Çabı and Yalçınalp, 2009). According to the definition made by Kaya and Varol, concern is "*normal anxiety, a fundamental response to danger, and a good feeling that allows someone to get adapted to the environment. The anxiety within normal limits is positive for self-protection, and it ends when the threat disappears.*" Anxiety can also lead to negative situations for individuals. Therefore, it affects both teacher training process and many other problems. Individuals need to manage their anxiety to eliminate this problem (Urgan, 2012).

In studies carried out with this regard, it has been found out that the concerns of the teacher candidates for non-appointment differ by various variables. It can be said that these concerns primarily include failing in KPSS (Public Personnel Selection Exam), and non-appointment. Baştürk (2007: 163) conducted a study on fourth grade teacher candidates studying in Pamukkale University Faculty of Education about their concerns of KPSS exam in 2004-2005 academic year. According to the results of "exam anxiety scale" applied to 192 teacher candidates; it has been determined that candidates have a high level of concern in total with Delusion and Affective dimensions, which are subscales. It has also been observed that male teacher candidates have a higher level of exam anxiety than female candidates; and elementary school teacher candidates have higher exam anxiety compared to primary school teacher candidates. The number of exam participants has also been determined to be effective.

In a qualitative research conducted to determine concerns of teacher candidates about teaching profession, Cabı and Yalçınalp (2009) have found out that teacher candidates have concerns about communication with students, employment, school life, economic life, professional acceptance and environment.

According to the findings of Doğan and Çoban (2009) obtained from their study to determine the attitudes and anxiety levels of fourth grade students studying 'Faculty of Education' in Gazi and Başkent University for teaching profession, it has been determined that attitudes of the students are positive, anxiety level is low and there is a low, negative and significant relationship between attitude and anxiety. In the study, it

has been found out that anxiety levels do not vary by gender. It has been seen that female students, those who recommend their profession to relatives, those who love their profession and those who are optimistic about finding a job have a more positive attitude. On the other hand, those who are pessimistic about finding a job are more anxious.

Pamuk, Hamurcu and Armağan (2014: 293) have also achieved similar results in their study on classroom teacher candidates studying in Buca Faculty of Education. When constant anxiety state of 234 fourth-grade teacher candidates is examined, it has been determined that anxiety state levels of teacher candidates are generally moderate. However, constant anxiety point average is higher than average anxiety state point. Considering gender, the constant anxiety level of female teacher candidates has been found significantly different from that of male candidates. In the analysis of the open-ended questions asked in the study, it has been seen that the teacher candidates expressed their concerns about employment, non-appointment, failing KPSS and family expectations in the first place.

In his study on the teacher candidates studying in different departments of Trakya University Faculty of Education, Eskici (2016: 361) has determined that non-appointment concern of teacher candidates is above the moderate level in general. It can be seen that female teachers' concern for non-appointment is much higher than that of male candidates, although there is no significant difference by branches.

İnce-Aka and Yilmaz (2018) studied non-appointment concerns of 80 teacher candidates studying in the fourth grade of Science Department. According to the obtained data, it has been determined that teacher candidates generally have a high level of non-appointment concern. It has been seen that there is no significant difference between non-appointment concerns of teacher candidates by gender.

It can be said that anxiety affects both human health and teacher candidates' motivation of learning and teaching. In general, motivation can be defined as all efforts that determine behavior of individuals (Ertürk, 1995). Motivation, in other words incentive, gives energy to individuals and mobilizes them to act in line with their goals. For this reason, students' motivation to learn is of great importance in the beginning of learning process (Erden and Akman, 1995: 232). In a study carried out by Ayık and Ates (2014), there is a positive, moderate and meaningful relationship between motivation of teacher candidates and their attitudes towards teaching profession. In addition, the attitudes of teacher candidates towards teaching profession are seen as a significant predictor of their motivation for teaching and internal - external motivation.

Considering effects of motivation, on the whole life of individuals, motivation of teachers in the training process is gaining much more importance. Their motivation to teach can have an influence on their preparations for the teaching process and their efforts. It is thought that teachers' effort to have professional improvement is thought to be related to their teaching motivation (Butler, 2007, Tittle, 2006, Watt and Richardson, 2007, Akt. Candan Güzel and Evin Gencil, 2015: 74). For this reason, determining the teaching motivation of teacher candidates can open the way for taking measures to increase their motivation.

In this context, it is seen important to determine the concerns of classroom teacher candidates for non-appointment and their motivation for teaching. The data to be obtained from this study is thought to be important in order to determine the current status and to make future studies.

Determining concerns of teacher candidates for non-appointment, their teaching motivation, and revealing the existence of possible relations between them constitute the problem status of this study. Answers to the following sub-problems have been sought in line with this problem status.

1. What is the level of concern of classroom teacher candidates for non-appointment?
2. Are the concerns of classroom teacher candidates for non-appointment vary by gender variable and the university they study?
3. What is the teaching motivation level of classroom teacher candidates?
4. Does the teaching motivation of classroom teacher candidates vary by gender and the university they study?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the concerns of classroom teacher candidates about non-appointment and their teaching motivation?

2. Method

The study was designed in screening model. The screening model is defined as a quantitative research approach that allows the attitude, tendency, or opinions of a research population to reach quantitative definitions by working on a sample from this population (Creswell, 1998, Fowler, 2009). In the survey research, the population and the sample are found, and the purpose is to obtain generalizable data while it is given great importance that the sample represents the population.

2.1 Population and Sample

The population of the study is fourth grade teacher candidates studying Classroom Teaching Department of Faculties of Education in Aegean, Black Sea and Marmara Region of Turkey in 2017-2018 academic year. The sample of the study consists of 370 teacher candidates selected from five different Faculties of Education by simple random sampling method. It is believed that the sample is sufficient, considering that it includes 450 fourth-grade candidates from five faculties. The universities included in the sample are identified with the names of A, B, C, D, E due to ethical concerns and not to cause different interpretations. A is located in the Black Sea region, B, D and E are located in the Aegean region, and C is located in the Marmara region.

2.2 Measurement Tools

In the study, non-appointment concern of classroom teacher candidates was measured by "Teacher Candidates' Non-Appointment Concern" Scale developed by Eskici (2016) and teaching motivation was measured by "Teaching Motivation Scale" adapted to Turkish by Candan and Evin Gencil (2015). Scales were implemented with the approval

of the instructors who developed them. Teacher Candidates' Non-Appointment Concern scale consists of 13 articles and it is in the form of 5-point Likert. The scale without negative article consists of two sub-dimensions. Fear for non-appointment (10 articles) and personal perception (3 articles). According to the results of the reliability analysis done by Eskici (2016: 368) who developed the scale, The Cronbach-alpha value was found to be .96. After the implementation in this study, the value was found to be .95. It can be said that the scale is highly reliable when considered in terms of the value found closed to each other and the criteria used to determine the reliability of a scale. As emphasized by Özdamar (1997) and Alpar (2003), in evaluating the Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient considering the whole scale, the scales with values between .60 and .80 are very reliable, and the scales with values ranging from .80 to 1.00; show that the scale is highly reliable.

The Teaching Motivation scale consists of 12 articles and 2 sub-dimensions. 7 articles have been drawn up for internal motivation and 5 articles for external motivation and it does not contain any adverse article. The scale is in the form of 6-point Likert. In the reliability analysis of Candan Güzel and Evin Gencil (2015: 72) who developed the scale, the Cronbach-alpha value was determined to be .92. The value after this implementation in this study was found to be .88. According to the values reached during the implementation process, these scales can also be said to be highly reliable.

Analysis of the research data was done by SPSS v.22 packaged software and ANOVA and t-test techniques and Pearson's Correlation techniques were used besides descriptive statistics. $p < .05$ level was used as base in the audit.

3. Findings and Comments

In this part of the study, the findings obtained from research questions are focused on and interpreted.

The first sub-problem question of the research has been stated as what is the level of concern of classroom teacher candidates for non - appointment? Descriptive statistics done in order to demonstrate this situation are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Results of the Non-appointment Concern Scale

Variables	n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	Median	Ranj	Minimum and Maximum Values
Non-appointment concern	370	50,01	12,30	52,00	52,00	13-65

As can be seen in Table 1, the non-appointment points are between 13-65. The total points that can be taken from the total of the scale vary between 13-65. In order to be able to interpret the arithmetic average points, the interval of points has also been determined. When calculated accordingly, I do not agree at all (13-23,4), I do not agree (23,5-33,8), No idea (33,9-44,2), Partly agree (44,3-54,6) and I agree is (54,7-65) points.

Considering non-appointment concern point average ($\bar{x}$ =50,01) of teacher candidates given in the table, it is seen that it is within the range of 'partly agree'. In this case, it can be said that in general, non-appointment concern levels of teacher candidates are high. The arithmetic mean reached by Eskici (2016), who developed the scale, is 47,49. It can be said that the values reached in this implementation are higher, even though both points are within the same range. This situation is thought to be caused by the changed appointment rules such as contractual appointment, increasing number of non-appointed teachers, and so on. These findings are similar to the findings of İnce-Aka and Yılmaz (2018).

The second sub-problem of the research has been stated as; Are the concerns of classroom teacher candidates for non-appointment vary by gender variable and the university they study? In order to reveal the findings of this sub-question, t-test and one-way analysis of variance were applied on the data. The findings are given in Table 2 below.

Table 2: t/F Test Results regarding Non-appointment concern
Points of Classroom Teacher Candidates

Variables		n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	sd	t/F	p
Gender	Female	300	50,50	12,16	368	1,57	,11
	Male	70	47,92	12,77			
University	University A	29	53,24	9,97	365	2,76	,02*
	University B	89	53,00	11,38			
	University C	113	48,81	12,30			
	University D	25	47,52	12,66			
	University E	114	48,59	13,04			

*p<0,05

As can also be seen in the table, teacher candidates' concern for non-appointment does not vary by gender. This result is similar to the result of some researches in the field, while contradicting with some others. Similar results were achieved in the studies of Arı and Yılmaz (2013), Ersoy and Küçükkaragöz (2010), Doğan and Çoban (2009) and İnce-Aka and Yılmaz (2018) and it has been seen that the gender variable does not make any difference. Whereas Ceyhan (2005) and Baştürk (2007) indicate that the concern levels of male teachers are high; Çakmak and Hevedanlı (2005) and Çetin (2013) state that women have higher level of anxiety. According to these results, it can be said that the anxiety levels of the teacher candidates can vary by various factors and this situation does not only depend only gender variable.

Considering differentiation by universities, it can be seen that University A and B have higher anxiety levels than the other three universities. This difference also caused a significant difference at the p <.05 level. It is seen that the difference is not caused by geographical locations. Because while the University A is in the Black Sea

region, Universities of B, D and E are in the Aegean region and D is in the Marmara region. In this case, it can be argued that the differences are caused by subjective conditions of universities, - number of students in the class, entry scores, rankings in KPSS, qualifications in the teaching process, and so on.

The third sub-problem of the research has been stated as; What is the teaching motivation level of classroom teacher candidates? Descriptive statistics are given in Table 3 to reveal this situation.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics Results of the Teaching Motivation Scale

Variables	n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	Median	Ranj	Minimum ve Maximum Values
Teaching Motivation	370	51,45	10,95	52,00	60,00	12-72

As seen in Table 3, teaching motivation points are between 12-72. In order to be able to interpret the arithmetic average points, the interval of points have also been determined. When calculated accordingly, I do not agree at all (12-22), I do not agree (22,1-32), I don't agree a little (32,1-42), I agree to some degree (42,1-52) and I agree is (52.1-62) points. Considering non-appointment concern point average ($\bar{x}$ =50,01) of teacher candidates given in the table, it is seen that it is within the range of 'partly agree'. Teaching motivation of teacher candidates can be said to be at the moderate level according to the teaching motivation scale point average ($\bar{x}$ =51,45). Candan Güzel and Evin Gencil (2015), who worked on the adaptation of the scale, reached 53,43 arithmetic average in their study. Their findings are similar to the results obtained from this research. It can be said that both groups are at the moderate level, indeed above the moderate level.

When the literature is examined, it is seen that there is limited number of studies on teaching motivation. It is seen that the studies on motivation address academic internal motivation (Uyulgan and Akkuzu, 2014) or motivations on specific fields such as science, reading, social sciences etc (Dede and Yaman, 2008, Yildiz, 2013, Tahiroğlu and Aktepe, 2015). The study of Ayık and Ataş (2014) regarding the teaching motivation was carried out with the candidate teachers studying at Atatürk University Kazim Karabekir Faculty of Education in the academic year of 2012-2013. The sample of the research consists of 294 teacher candidates. Teaching motivation and teacher candidates' attitudes towards teaching profession have been examined in the study and a positive, moderate and significant relationship has been found between them. In addition, it has been determined that the attitudes of teacher candidates towards the teaching profession are meaningful predictors of the teaching motives of teacher candidates, and their internal and external motivations. For this reason, it is thought that the findings obtained from this study will contribute considerably to the literature.

The fourth sub-problem of the study has been stated as; Does the teaching motivation of classroom teacher candidates vary by gender and the university they

study? In order to reveal the findings of this question, t-test and ANOVA were applied again. Findings are given in Table 4.

Table 4: t/F Test Results of Fourth-grade Classroom Teacher Candidates regarding their Teaching Motivation Points

Variables		n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	sd	t/F	p
Gender	Female	300	51,63	10,72	368	,67	,50
	Male	70	50,65	11,94			
University	University A	29	49,44	10,08	365	5,51	,00*
	University B	89	55,80	11,79			
	University C	113	49,12	10,56			
	University D	25	49,96	9,38			
	University E	114	51,19	10,35			

*p<0,05

As seen in the table, teaching motivations of teacher candidates do not vary by gender. It is seen that arithmetic mean of female or male teachers' candidates' teaching motivation is close to each other. Considering that the highest score is 72 and the lowest score is 12, it can be said that the teaching motivation is moderate in both groups.

When examined by universities, a significant difference is seen. It can be said that the universities where teacher candidates study are influential on their motivation for teaching. It is seen that all groups have a moderate level of teaching motivation; however, a university in the Aegean region has a higher arithmetic average compared to the others. It is believed that this significant difference is caused by subjective conditions of the University rather than the regional conditions.

The last subproblem of the study is stated as; is there a significant relationship between the concerns of classroom teacher candidates about non-appointment and their teaching motivation? Pearson's Correlation analysis was performed to reveal the findings of this question. Findings are given in Table-5.

Table 5: Pearson's Correlation Results between non-appointment concern and attitudes of Classroom Teacher Candidates towards their Teaching Motivation

	Values	Teaching Motivation
	r	,12
Concern for Non-appointment	p	0,01*
	N	370

*p<0,05

When Table 5 is examined, it is concluded that there is a very weak but positive and significant relationship between the non-appointment concern and teaching motivation

of classroom teacher candidates who participated in the study ($r = .12$; $p < .05$). This result can be interpreted as 'teacher candidates have hopes despite their concern for non-appointment and they do not reflect this to their teaching motive.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has been carried out to examine the concerns of classroom teacher candidates for non-appointment and their motivation for teaching. According to the findings obtained, classroom teachers' concern for non-appointment has been found above medium level and significant differences have been determined by universities. It has been determined that although the anxiety is above medium level, teacher candidates do not lose their teaching motivation for teaching and their teaching motivation points are still above the medium level. In addition, it has been determined that the motivation of teacher candidates varies significantly by universities. No significant difference has been found between the genders in both variables. Furthermore, it has been concluded that there is a very weak but positive and significant relationship between the non-appointment concern and teaching motivation of classroom teacher candidates.

Comments and discussions regarding the results obtained are given below tables. For that reason, this section only focuses on recommendations.

1. Findings reveal the existence of non-appointment concern of teacher candidates. In order to reduce this concern, it is suggested to carry out various studies by either MEB (Ministry of National Education) or universities educating teachers (quota determination, increasing the number of appointments).
2. It has been indicated before that in the literature there are limited number of studies on teaching motivation. For this reason, findings obtained from this study are considered to be a sample to new studies on teacher training process and teaching processes.
3. From the findings of this study, it can be recommended to carry out qualitative research related to the concerns of teacher candidates for non-appointment.
4. The sample of this research only consists of Classroom teacher candidates. The number of appointments made according to the results of KPSS varies by branches. Generally, teachers with the highest number of appointments are classroom teachers. For this reason, it may be advised to examine non-appointment concern of teacher candidates in this branch and in the other branches who have less chance to be appointed.
5. It can be considered that it may be appropriate, especially for universities educating teacher, to provide different activities to reduce concern, stress of teacher candidates (counseling programs, different hobbies and support activities, refresher courses in fields where students feel themselves inadequate)

References

1. Alpar, R. (2003). *Uygulamalı çok değişkenli istatistiksel yöntemlere giriş 1*. Ankara: Nobel Yayınları.
2. Arı, E & Yılmaz, V. (2015). KPSS hazırlık kursuna devam eden öğretmen adaylarının umutsuzluk düzeyleri. *Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences*, 14 (4), 905-931.
3. Ayık, A. & Ataş, Ö. (2013). Öğretmen adaylarının öğretmenlik mesleğine yönelik tutumları ile öğretme motivasyonları arasındaki ilişki. *Journal of Educational Sciences Research*, 4 (1), 25-43.
4. Baştürk, R. (2007). Kamu personeli seçme sınavına hazırlanan öğretmen adaylarının sınav kaygı düzeylerinin incelenmesi. *Fırat Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 17 (2), 163-176.
5. Cabı, E., & Yalçınalp S., (2009). Öğretmen adaylarının mesleki ve eğitim teknolojilerini kullanma kaygı düzeylerine yönelik görüşleri. IV. International Educational Technology Conference, Hacettepe University, p. 579.
6. Candan Güzel, D.&Evin Gencil, İ.(2015) . Öğretme motivasyonu ölçeği'ni Türkçe'ye uyarlama çalışması. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 36, 72-89.
7. Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
8. Çakmak, Ö. & Hevedanlı, M. (2005). Eğitim ve fen-edebiyat fakülteleri biyoloji bölümü öğrencilerinin kaygı düzeylerinin çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenmesi. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 4 (14), 115-127.
9. Çetin, Ş. (2013). Eğitim fakültesi öğrencilerinin kamu personeli seçme sınavına (kpss) yönelik kaygılarının incelenmesi. *The Journal of National Education*, 197, 158-167.
10. Dede, Y. & Yaman, S. (2008) Fen öğrenmeye yönelik motivasyon ölçeği: Geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması. *Necatibey Eğitim Fakültesi Elektronik Fen ve Matematik Eğitimi Dergisi (EFMED)*, 2 (1),19-37.
11. Doğan, T. & Çoban, A. E. (2009). Eğitim fakültesi öğrencilerinin öğretmenlik mesleğine yönelik tutumları ile kaygı düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. *Eğitim ve Bilim*,34(153), 157-168.
12. Erden, M. & Akman, Y. (1995). *Eğitim psikolojisi*, Ankara: Arkadaş yayıncılık.
13. Ersoy, E. & Küçükkaragöz, H. (2010). Öğretmen adaylarının umutsuzluk düzeylerinin bazı değişkenlere göre belirlenmesi. *e-Journal of New World Science Academy*, 5 (4), 1535-1542.
14. Ertürk, M. (1995). *İşletmelerde Yönetim ve Organizasyon*, İstanbul: Beta Basım Yayın.
15. Eskici, M. (2016) Öğretmen adaylarının atanamama kaygılarının çeşitli değişkenlere göre incelenmesi. *Turkish Studies*, 11 (19), 361-378.

16. İnce-Aka, E. & Yılmaz, M. (2018). Fen bilimleri öğretmen adaylarının atanamama kaygılarının incelenmesi üzerine bir araştırma. *Eğitim ve Toplum Araştırmaları Dergisi (JRES)*, 5 (1), 105-123.
17. Fowler, F. J. (2009). *Survey research methods (4th ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
18. Kaya, M. & Varol, K. (2004). İlahiyat fakültesi öğrencilerinin durumluk-sürekli kaygı düzeyleri ve kaygı nedenleri (Samsun örneği). *Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi İlahiyat Fakültesi Dergisi*, (17), 32-63.
19. Özdamar, K. (1997). Paket programlar ile istatistiksel veri analizi-1. Eskişehir: Anadolu Üniversitesi Yayınları 1001/11.
20. Pamuk, Y., Hamurcu, H. & Armağan, B. (2014) Sınıf öğretmeni adaylarının durumluk ve sürekli kaygı düzeylerinin incelenmesi (İzmir-Buca Örneği). *Bartın University Journal of Faculty of Education*, 3 (2), 293-316.
21. Tahiroğlu, M. & Aktepe, V. (2015). 4. ve 5. sınıf sosyal bilgiler dersi motivasyon ölçeği formunun geçerlilik ve güvenilirlik çalışması. *Turkish Studies*, 10 (3), 907-932.
22. Urgan, R. (2012). Bilim kaygının olumlu yönlerini keşfediyor. Cumhuriyet Bilim Teknik Dergisi. Access date: 01.04.2018 http://www.cumhuriyet.com.tr/haber/diger/338094/Bilim_kayginin_olumlu_yonl_erni_kesfediyor.html
23. Uyulgan, M., A. & Akkuzu, N. (2014). Öğretmen adaylarının akademik içsel motivasyonlarına bir bakış. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 14 (1), 7-32.
24. Yıldız, M. (2013). Okuma Motivasyonu, Akıcı Okuma ve Okuduğunu Anlamanın Beşinci Sınıf Öğrencilerinin Akademik Başarılarındaki Rolü, *Turkish Studies*, 8 (4), 1461-1478.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).